

SEMANCO: Semantic Tools for Carbon Reduction in Urban Planning

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ABSTRACT: The goal of the SEMANCO project is to develop an ontology-based energy information system and associated tools that help stakeholders involved in urban planning to make informed decisions about how to reduce CO₂ emissions in cities. An ontology system is to be developed from the requirement analysis performed at the case studies. This approach enables data, services and stakeholders to be taken into account in the process of building ontologies. To create the ontology-based system we have adopted a decentralized approach according to which modular ontologies from diverse domains become interlinked through a semantic framework. In this paper we summarize the project vision and discuss some research issues currently being developed in the project concerning ontologies for energy information at the urban level, multi-scale analysis of carbon reduction problems and integration of GIS with linked data.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 *Applying ontologies to energy information*

During the last four years, we have been developing a line of research aimed at applying ICT to the modelling and analysis of energy information first at the building scale and later on at the urban level. In the IntUBE project carried out from 2008 to 2011 within the 7th Framework Programme, we have proposed an energy information integration platform (EIIP) to capture the energy information flow throughout the different stages of the whole building life cycle (Böhms et al. 2010). The platform was composed of four data repositories to store building, simulation and performance data generated throughout the different stages of the building life cycle. An OWL ontology was created to model the data in each repository according to the knowledge provided by domain experts. Later on, in the RÉPENER project co-financed by the Spanish 2009-2012 National RDI plan, we have moved from the idea of an integrated platform to the creation of an energy information system which integrates both proprietary and open data, following the initiative of the Linked Open Data movement. In this project, we have created an energy model based on existing energy information standards which encompass building data as well as the contextual data –climate, economic and social– which impact buildings’ energy efficiency. Based on this model, we have created local ontologies which

integrate proprietary and public data and present the data on the Internet using RDF language (Madrazo et al. 2012). Lastly, in 2011 we started the SEMANCO project –also co-funded by the 7th Framework Programme– whose purpose is to apply semantic technologies to modelling energy information at the urban scale. In this paper, we will introduce the project's aim and discuss some areas of the research which are currently under development concerning the design of ontologies for energy data at the urban level, modelling of complex systems, and integration of GIS with linked data.

2 SEMANCO: THE PROJECT’S AIM

2.1 *Project scope and structure*

Continuing with the work we developed in the IntUBE and RÉPENER projects, the purpose of SEMANCO is to create a system of energy information using semantic web technologies which –unlike the previous projects– is not limited to buildings but extends to the urban scale. Specifically, the objective of SEMANCO is to provide methods and tools, based on semantic modelling of energy information, to help different stakeholders involved in urban planning to make informed decisions about how to reduce CO₂ emissions in cities.

- Supporting access to, and analysis of, distributed and heterogeneous sources of energy related data, both open and proprietary
- Semantic modelling of energy data according to energy and ontology standards
- Integrated tools that access and update the semantically modelled data, based on new and existing IT solutions for decision making in development of CO₂ reduction strategies
- An analysis of requirements to ensure that the tools and CO₂ reduction strategies developed address real world problems represented by the case studies.

2.2 Semantic Energy Information Framework

A key component of this research is the design and implementation of the Semantic Energy Information Framework (SEIF). This framework is the nexus between the different data sources and the tools which use the semantically modelled data (Fig. 1). The semantic mapping will act as a bridge between different domains (city planning and energy provision) and contents (consumption data, pollution sources, simulated energy profiles and benchmarks). This semantic model will support interoperability among systems by enabling translation and mapping between different modelling methods and tools to support decision making in urban planning. Through the SEIF, a set of analysis and visualization tools to be developed in the project will access the heterogene-

ous and distributed databases containing different types of energy related information. This data integration is done with ontology matching techniques which are well-known and have proved to interrelate heterogeneous data sources (Euzenat 2011).

Semantic data integration will require defining a local ontology for each data source. The SEIF implicitly contains an energy model which provides the necessary language to understand and interpret the complexity of different data sources and their inter-relationships. The energy model is implemented as a global ontology which embraces all terms that the tools need to interact with the SEIF. The energy model ontology and the local ontologies use the OWL standard language, and data is presented on the Internet using the RDF language following the Linked Open Data (LOD) initiative.

The terminology contained in the semantic energy model is based on international energy and environmental standards. Nowadays, ISO standards are all in terms of the building scale, and –to the best of our knowledge– there are no specific International Standards for energy modelling at the urban scale. However, starting from analysis at the building scale, the ISO standards also can be indirectly applied to urban energy modelling. This statement is confirmed by the majority of studies on urban energy modelling, which have been carried out based on energy assessments of reference (representative) buildings and then extrapolated through analysis to the urban area by applying statistical data (Brownword 2005, Jones 2001 & Yamaguchi 2003).

Figure 1. Structure of the SEMANCO project.

Specifically, energy model terminology is specified in ISO/IEC CD 13273 (Energy efficiency and renewable energy sources), ISO/DTR 16344 (Common terms, definitions and symbols for the overall energy performance rating and certification of buildings), ISO/CD 16346 (Assessment of overall energy performance of buildings), ISO/DIS 12655 (Presentation of real energy use of buildings), ISO/CD 16343 (Methods for expressing energy performance and for energy certification of buildings), and ISO 50001:2011 (Energy management systems – Requirements with guidance for use).

2.3 Integration of multiple scales

The problem of CO₂ emissions reduction is difficult to delimit to a particular geographical area. It is a systemic problem in which multiple dimensions and geographical scales need to be integrated. For instance, we can focus the description and analysis of an urban system on different scales: at building, neighbourhood, district or city level, among others. The existence of multiple scales conveys important challenges to be addressed in the analytical process concerning carbon emissions: the relevant aspect considered to perceive and represent the system would change depending on the chosen analytical scale. In order to address the multiple dimensions involved in the problem of CO₂ emission reduction, the tools and methods developed in SEMANCO will integrate the various geographic scales at different demonstration scenarios (Fig. 2).

Through the SEIF, the energy data associated

Figure 2. Integration of multiple geographic scales in the case studies.

with the different geographic scales will become interrelated (Fig. 3). The SEIF provides data that the analysis and visualization tools need for a specific task at a given scale. Conversely, the outcomes generated by these tools enhance the energy model implicit in the semantic framework.

2.4 Research methodology

The methodology adopted in the research is based on a case study approach. Different scenarios located in Denmark, Spain and the United Kingdom will enable delimiting the scope of the research and defining the specifications for the tools needed by stakeholders in different domains: planners working on the development of new areas or the renovation of existing ones; policy makers setting targets and regulations to reduce carbon emissions, and citizens applying energy efficiency measures in public and private buildings. Furthermore, the demonstration scenarios will help to:

1. Identify relevant indicators; interrelationships between factors contributing to CO₂ reduction; emission reduction strategies; baselines for energy consumption; and uses of energy efficient and renewable energy technologies;

2. Verify effectiveness of tools and methods; reductions of energy consumption and CO₂ emissions; social impact; improved indoor environmental qualities (IEQ); and investment costs.

In order to create the energy model embedded in the SEIF, it is necessary to compile a set of existing data sources and a set of tools which make use of the data within a limited application realm or use case. In the context of this research, a use case delimits a research problem concerning carbon reduction in a specific domain. The use case describes how actors, tools and data interrelate in order to fulfil a strategic goal.

3 PROJECT DEVELOPMENT

In this section we discuss some of the project areas which are currently being developed regarding the creation of ontologies for energy information in urban environments, multi-scale analysis of energy systems, and integration of GIS and linked data.

3.1 Ontologies for energy information in urban environments

As Guarino & Giaretta (1995) had explained, within the knowledge engineering community “ontology” refers to a particular object rather to a discipline (e.g. the philosophical notion of Ontology). This object can be thought of as an informal conceptual system, a formal semantic account and “an explicit specification of a conceptualization”, as Gruber (1993) had defined it. Considering ontology from a technical point of view, a clear distinction should be made between “an ontology intended as a particular conceptual framework at the semantic level and an ontology intended as a concrete artefact at the syntactic

Figure 3. SEMANCO technological platform.

level to be used for a given purpose” (Guarino & Giarretta 1995).

In the context of the current level of development of the semantic web, ontologies make it possible to connect different views of the world fostered by different disciplines and domains which are embedded in the information structure of different data sources. More recently, the linked open data initiative has provided a new impulse towards the transformation of the web in a global knowledge base (Heath 2011).

3.1.1 *Ontologies, energy and geographic information*

Although in the recent literature we find applications of semantic technologies to specific domains related to energy efficiency in buildings –operation, interoperability, smart grid (Kofler et al. 2012, Noguero et al. 2011, Han et al. 2011, Kabitzsch & Ploennings 2011 & Wagner et al. 2010) – not much work has been done so far with regard to using the ontologies to integrate energy data from different domains in an urban context. Nor have we been able to find references to application of ontologies to represent the complex interaction between data from multiple domains –social, economic and urban– involved in the modelling and understanding of carbon emissions in urban environments. Further difficulties to be overcome have to do with difficulty obtaining the data that is necessary for energy efficiency research (Lannon & Linovski 2009).

The integration of urban energy models with GIS systems using ontologies, however, opens up an area of research which will require systems able to cap-

ture the relationships between buildings rather than the buildings themselves; the interaction between different levels of the built environment (between buildings and streets, for example); and changes over time (Lannon & Linovski 2009). Even though there are many environments to manage ontologies, so far they have not been dedicated to modelling of geographic information (Zaki et al. 2009).

3.1.2 *Ontology design*

Ontology design conveys a process of knowledge sharing between a community of users (domain experts, users of semantic-based applications) and ontology engineers. It also requires having access to existing data sources (proprietary and public) and defining the relationships between data based on the use that will be made of that data (by application services and different users). Adding semantic meaning to data, therefore, is inextricably related to the use that will be made of these data in a particular context. The case study approach adopted in the project brings together actors, data and services within a particular frame, which we refer to as “use case”. This approach enables us to take into consideration the user’s needs, in order to ensure that ontological systems are of use to different stakeholders involved in urban planning (Lannon & Linovski 2009).

The process of creating an ontology requires a certain methodology, and precisely this lack of established methodologies is one of the difficulties to overcome. As Gómez & Benjamins (1999) contended, “The ontology building process is a craft rather than an engineering activity. Each develop-

Figure 7. Integration of the SEIF with 3dMaps GIS software.

data to the platform, populating the spatial database with GIS data and maintaining the 3D web cache with updated optimized data. This server will also facilitate the different tools implemented for the data in the SEMANCO project and provide a layer for interoperability between the tools. The storage of GIS data and persistent data created by the tools will be handled by a Spatial Database. The Application server stores and fetches data when needed from the Spatial DB. The 3D data could be stored in a structure similar to 3D City Database in order to use the OGC standard CityGML internally as well as for input and output to the platform.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In the SEMANCO project we have adopted a comprehensive approach to modelling energy information at the urban scale using ontologies. In this context, ontologies would help: 1. to integrate data at multiple geographic scales; 2. to capture domain expert knowledge; 3. to interrelate different domains involved in the evaluation of CO₂ emissions; and 4. to exchange data generated by various applications (interoperability across GIS, simulation programs, and sensor systems).

The decentralized approach based on interlinked semantic databases driven by the linked open data community is one of the pillars of the SEMANCO project. The purpose is to make use of a net of interconnected standards (e.g. CityGML, ISO/IEC CD 13273, ISO/DTR 16344) rather than placing a particular standard at the core of the energy information system. In this context, our goal is to create expressive ontologies –rather than vocabularies– to model

data as well as perform data analysis and inference processes.

In order to build the ontologies, we have adopted a methodology based on the integration of data sources, services and actors around a particular use case. A use case provides the specifications necessary to design the ontologies, while it ensures that the data and analysis processes will be of use for a particular group of stakeholders in the actual world.

5 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

SEMANCO is being carried out with the support of the 7th Framework Program “ICT for Energy Systems” 2011-2014. We would like to thank our colleagues in the project consortium for the assistance provided to prepare this document: Ilaria Ballarini and Vincenzo Corrado, from Politecnico di Torino, for the information on energy standards, and Johan Göransson and Tomas Karlsson, from Agency9, for the descriptions of 3dMaps software.

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